

A Mixed Reality System for Investigating Expert Characteristics on Recall of Situation Including Self-Motion

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Abstract: To study recall accuracy of the offensive and defensive situations including movements of elite-athlete/novice oneself, a novel experimental system was developed where defensive actions were performed by the subject with a CG (Computer Graphics) player who presented predetermined offensive actions. Both the CG player's movements and subject's movements were reproduced by a video using mixed reality technology for recall examination. This system was also designed to rearrange the natural sequence of image frames resulting in a reproducible video in which the time relation of offense and defense was falsified. Displacement of timing in the false video was twofold; delayed from the truth or advanced from the truth. Using this two-video, true/false imagery method, the subject was asked to select the true video by recall; thus it became possible to examine the recall accuracy quantitatively by controlling the timing displacement. Results of the experiment using this system revealed that karate expert possessed a skill to recognize the time relation between the opponent's movement and one's own movement perceptually that was more developed than that of the novice. It was further identified that the expert as well as the novice recognized delayed displacement more accurately than they could recognize advanced displacement.

Key words: Mixed reality, recall paradigm, perceptual cognitive skill, computer graphics, displacement of timing.

1. Introduction

A number of research protocols have been used to elicit expertise differences in perceptual and cognitive skill in sport [1]. The recall paradigm is a research model for assessing the degree to which the expert maintains a cognitive advantage over the lesser skilled performer [2]. This paradigm involves displaying a

task-specific video image to an athlete, after which the subject must recall the situation. Performance is then ascertained as the level of the subject's recall accuracy of the situation in the display. Findings from numerous studies conducted using this paradigm have described experts as superior in recall tasks in their respective domains compared with novice athletes [3-6].

In competitive sports (e.g., martial arts), athletes have to react to opponent actions immediately and probably possesses the skill to well recognize offensive and defensive situation including self-motion. Nevertheless, the studies conducted until now on recall paradigm required subjects to only observe the video image and to recall the situation after the observation. There are no studies on recall situations including actions performed

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by the subjects, and no methods for examining recall accuracy of the time relationship between opponent actions and one's own actions in offensive and defensive situation have been established.

To study recall accuracy of the offensive and defensive situations including movements of the subject oneself, we developed a mixed reality system where defensive actions were performed by the subject with a CG (Computer Graphics) player who presented predetermined offensive actions. Both the CG player movements and subject's movements were reproduced by a video using mixed reality technology [7] for recall examination. This method was also designed to rearrange the natural sequence of image frames resulting in a reproducible video in which the time relation of offense and defense was falsified. Displacement of timing in the false video was twofold; delayed from the truth or advanced from the truth. Using this two-video, true/false imagery method, the subject was asked to select the true video by recall; thus it becomes possible to examine the recall accuracy quantitatively by controlling the timing displacement.

In this study, we examined martial artist's (karate expert's) skill used to recognize the time relationship by using our system. The time relationship is particularly important in a martial art match.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the mixed reality system. The experiment for investigating recall skill using the system is shown in section 3. Sections 4-5 describe the results of the experiment and discussion on the result respectively. Section 6 gives conclusions.

2. Mixed Reality System

The mixed reality system consisted of a personal computer (2.00 GHz CPU, 3.00 GB memory), a high-speed video camera (frame rate: 110 Hz, 320 × 240 pixels), a video projector (refresh rate: 60 Hz, 1024 × 768 pixels) and a screen. The computer primarily controlled camera image input, image synthesis processing, outputting of CG images, and synthesized

images to the projector (See Fig. 1).

Fig. 2 presents the flow of image synthesis processing. The computer generated a time stamp for each CG animation image frame that was projected on the screen and each image frame of the subject's response movement filmed by the video camera. CG animation and subject response frames with matching time stamps were combined to allow for synthesis of a video where offense and defense were truly reproduced. Next, time positions of frames were displaced from each other to synthesize a false video in which the time relation is displaced (advanced/delayed) arbitrarily.

Spatial alignment in the synthesis was conducted using markers (See Fig. 1) that are commonly used in mixed reality technology [8]. The system superimposed the CG player on the marker in the filmed image including subject image. Motion data of the CG player were obtained by high-speed 3-dimensional motion capture (Sampling 240Hz, Motion Analysis Corp.). One karate expert who did not participate in the experiment performed rush and punch karate movements (Tobikomi Kizami-tsuki) with reflective markers attached to his body. Three dimensional kinetics were used to reconstruct motion data of this subject as he performed rush and punch karate movements.

3. Experiment

3.1 Participants

Test subjects who participated in this study consisted of 16 karate novices (16 males, average age of 26.9 years, SD = 6.7) and 16 karate experts (14 males and 2 females, average age of 27.3 years, SD = 7.9). The karate experts were members of the Canadian Shotokan Karate Association and had black belts with at least 6 years of experience. The novices with no previous martial art experiences were students or researchers at the University of Calgary. All participants were healthy and had normal or corrected-to-normal vision. Before the experiment, the purpose and methods of the study were explained and University of Calgary approved consent was received.

Fig. 1 Experiment layout. A CG player was projected on the screen so that the subject would react to the CG player's action. After the reaction, both the CG player movements and subject's movements were reproduced on the screen by using mixed reality technology.

Fig. 2 Representation of video image time displacement. Depiction of how images were either advanced or delayed in relation to the original image.

3.2 Procedure

The subject stood 3.5 m from the projection screen. Their feet were slightly longer than shoulder-width apart with the dominant foot forward. Both hands were held between the chest and abdomen as a fighting pose of boxing. For the left-handed subjects, the CG player was projected on the screen while the right and left were reversed by mirror reversal. The image projected was of the CG player rushing the subject and throwing a punch toward the face. From the subject's pose, she/he was requested to deflect the punch by twisting her/his upper body transversely. Movements of the subject from the waist up were collected by a video camera which was located behind the subject.

There were four steps to the trial procedure:

- (1) Projection of a front-view, life-sized image of the karate CG player's rush and punch motion on the screen;
- (2) Filming the subject's response movement by a video camera;
- (3) False reproduced image prepared based on the timing displacement being input by the person in charge of experiment (to be designated by displacement amount of the frame) and true reproduced image were presented alternately to the subject. The order of presentation of true and false images was determined randomly for each trial. If requested by the subject, true and false images were presented repeatedly;
- (4) The subject was requested to identify the true reproduced image by recalling the offensive and defensive situation performed just before.

The procedure was repeated by the Transformed Up-Down Method [9] while controlling the displacement amount. Lastly, the displacement amount when true and false images could not be distinguished was defined as a threshold of displacement and was recorded as recall accuracy for the subject. In the experimental trial, a 30 sec break was provided every 10 trials.

The procedure was performed for each of advancement displacement and delay displacement, so the threshold of displacement (recall accuracy) existed for each displacement. Both advancement displacement and delay displacement were mixed without fixing the order.

As rehearsal prior to the experiment, all subjects performed the procedure 10 times in which displacement of the frame was set to 25. The frame number 25 was determined by the preliminary experiment so that any subjects could distinguish the true video from the false video. Each subject was presented with five advancement and five time delays in random order in the rehearsal.

4. Results

The average of thresholds of displacement by experts ($n = 16$) and novices ($n = 16$) for each type of displacement are shown in Fig. 3. The displacement amount is shown using frame number. From observing the results in the figure, it can be seen that experts showed more accurate recall than novices for both advanced and delayed displacement. Interestingly, the threshold of delay displacement was smaller than that of advancement displacement for both experts and novices.

The thresholds were analyzed using a two-way repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Skill (two levels: Novice, Expert) as a between-subject factor and Displacement (two levels: Advancement, Delay) as a within-subject factor. Statistical significance was set at $p = 0.05$. The Skill factor was $F(1, 30) = 11.52$, $p < 0.01$, $\eta^2p = 0.28$, statistical power = 0.91, the Stimulus factor was $F(1, 30) = 51.49$, $p < 0.05$, $\eta^2p = 0.63$, statistical power = 1.00, and the Skill \times Stimulus interaction was $F(1, 30) = 2.98$, $p = 0.09$, $\eta^2p = 0.09$, statistical power = 0.39, where η^2p represents partial eta-squared value, which is an index of effect size when using a two-way or multi-way ANOVA. The Skill factor and the Stimulus factor were significant, but their interaction did not show significance.

Fig. 3 Mean values of thresholds of displacement (frame numbers) that subjects could perceive. Error bars indicate standard errors of mean.

5. Discussion

Results of ANOVA for skill factors show that the capability of a karate expert to recall offensive and defensive situations was superior to that of a novice. Studies of perceptual cognitive skill of elite athletes which have been presented thus far have revealed remarkable perceptual cognitive skill of a match situation (e.g., position information of the opposing player) [2] and excellent perceptual cognitive skill of one's own position and posture [10]. Results from this study show that the karate expert possesses a skill to recognize the time relation between an opponent's movement and one's own movement perceptually. Because an opponent's movement is recognized from visual information and one's own position and posture are recognized by proprioceptive information, it may be stated that the expert has excellent information processing skills for integrating them. According to the skilled-memory theory [11], experts encode information using existing semantic memory patterns. By nature of becoming an expert athlete, patterns of offensive and defensive skills have been learned through practice. It might be said that experts use

pattern recognition in information processing of integration.

ANOVA results reveal that, because no interaction was shown, the subjects recognized delay displacement more accurately than advancement displacement, irrespective of skill. In the recall test, the subjects compared the time relation of offensive and defensive movements in the memory with time relation of movements in reproduced images. There might be advancement displacement in the time relation in the memory. Studies by Libet [12-13] showed intracerebral phenomena designated as “backward causation” because of the fact that awareness of initiating a movement in healthy subjects is reported by the agent before the movement actually occurs. Verification of this phenomenon has advanced since then in the field of brain science study, and its mechanism has been identified gradually [14]. According to this backward causation, the subject perceives the timing of his own movement as starting earlier than the actual time. This is then memorized, and the possibility exists that the subject got the wrong idea that he performed his own movement earlier than the actual deed. Consequently, the present result can be explained such that the subject was more sensitive to delay displacement than to advancement displacement.

From what has been discussed above, the mixed reality system has worked well as an experimental tool for studying perceptual and cognitive skill in offensive and defensive situation including self-motion. We can say that the system will be one of the useful instruments for sport skill study.

6. Conclusions

To study recall characteristics of offensive and defensive situations including movements of the karate expert/novice oneself, we developed a mixed reality system to use a video reproduction. Using this system, the combination of image frames to be synthesized was displaced intentionally to produce a reproduced video in which the time relation between offense and defense

was falsified, videos of two types, true and false, were shown to the subject and he was asked to select the true video by recall. Displacement of timing in the false video was twofold; delayed from the truth or advanced from the truth, and it is now possible in each case to check the accuracy of recall of the time relation quantitatively.

Results of the experiment using this system revealed that the karate expert possessed a skill to recognize the time relation between the opponent’s movement and his own movement perceptually that was more developed than that of the novice. It was further identified that the expert as well as the novice recognized lagged displacement more accurately than advanced displacement. Although backward causation is regarded as the explanation for this, influences on motor recall should be investigated further in the future.

Lastly, the mixed reality system has worked well as an experimental tool for studying perceptual and cognitive skill in offensive and defensive situation including self-motion.

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